

1 **Quantitative determination of fentanyl in newborn pig plasma and cerebrospinal fluid samples by**
2 **HPLC-MS/MS**

3 *M. E. Blanco^{1*}, E. Encinas², O. González^{1,3}, E. Rico¹, V. Vozmediano⁴, E. Suárez², R.M. Alonso¹*

4 *¹ Analytical Chemistry Department, Science and Technology Faculty, University of the Basque Country*
5 *(UPV/EHU), Bilbao, Basque Country (Spain)*

6 *² Pharmacology Department, Faculty of Medicine, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Bilbao,*
7 *Basque Country (Spain)*

8 *³ Analytical Bioscience Division, LACDR, Leiden University, Leiden (The Netherlands)*

9 *⁴ Drug Modeling & Consulting, Dynakin, SL, Bilbao, Basque Country (Spain)*

10

11 **Corresponding author: M.E. Blanco*

12 *Postal address: Analytical Chemistry Department, Science and Technology Faculty, University of the*
13 *Basque Country (UPV/EHU), P.O. Box 644, 48080 Bilbao, Basque Country (Spain)*

14 *e-mail: mariaencarnacion.blanco@ehu.es*

15

16 *Keywords: fentanyl, newborn pig, plasma, cerebrospinal fluid, HPLC-MS/MS*

17

18 **Abstract**

19 In this study, a selective and sensitive high performance liquid chromatography-tandem
20 mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS) method requiring low sample volume ($\leq 100 \mu\text{L}$) was
21 developed and validated for the quantitative determination of the opioid drug fentanyl in
22 plasma and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). A protein precipitation extraction with acetonitrile
23 was used for plasma samples whereas CSF samples were injected directly on the
24 HPLC column. Fentanyl and $^{13}\text{C}_6$ -fentanyl (Internal Standard) were analysed in an
25 electrospray ionization source in positive mode, with multiple reaction monitoring (MRM)
26 of the transitions m/z 337.0/188.0 and m/z 337.0/105.0 for quantification and
27 confirmation of fentanyl, and m/z 343.0/188.0 for $^{13}\text{C}_6$ -fentanyl. The respective lowest
28 limits of quantification for plasma and CSF were 0.2 and 0.25 ng/mL. Intra- and inter-
29 assay precision and accuracy did not exceed 15%, in accordance with bioanalytical
30 validation guidelines. The described analytical method was proven to be robust and was
31 successfully applied to the determination of fentanyl in plasma and CSF samples from a
32 pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic study in newborn piglets receiving intravenous
33 fentanyl (5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bolus immediately followed by a 90-min infusion of 3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{h}$).

34

35 **Introduction**

36 Fentanyl (1-N-phenyl-N-(1-(2-phenylethyl)piperidyl)propanamide, FEN) is a synthetic μ -
37 opioid agonist used in neonatal and paediatric critical care units to provide analgesia
38 and/or sedation when administered in continuous intravenous infusion during and after
39 surgery [1] or in mechanically ventilated patients [2,3]. However, FEN administration is
40 not indicated in infants (i.e., below 2 years of age) according to the manufacturer's
41 product license, and the drug is therefore used off-label in this population. In order to
42 increase the knowledge on the product within this context and to try to reduce the
43 degree of empiricism currently associated with the establishment of dosing regimens in
44 this population, a maturation-physiology-based predictive
45 pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamics (PK/PD) model for fentanyl in neonatal care was
46 built [4]. The performance of a PK/PD study in a suitable animal species was
47 subsequently deemed convenient, as a complement and preliminary confirmation to the
48 developed theoretical model. Concretely, the newborn piglet was considered a
49 representative model of FEN behaviour in neonates because many of its anatomical
50 and physiological characteristics more closely resemble those of humans than other
51 non-primate species [5,6], as supported by the frequent use of preterm and term
52 neonate pigs in paediatric research [7–9]. In this respect, cytochrome P450 isoform 3A4
53 (CYP3A4), the enzyme responsible for hepatic fentanyl biotransformation in humans, is
54 also present in pigs with comparable levels and activity [5,10,11]. Moreover, the
55 differences observed between juvenile and adult pig PK for some drugs were deemed
56 as consistent with ontogenic changes reported for human PK [12]. Additionally, the
57 swine cardiovascular system and its physiological development (related with the PD) are

58 almost identical to those of humans [6,13]. The general objective of this kind of
59 experimental PK/PD studies is to characterize the systemic exposure of the drug after a
60 given dose (assessed by plasma levels) as well as its relationship with the observed
61 pharmacological effects. Nevertheless, FEN, a centrally acting drug that has to cross
62 the blood-brain barrier to exert the majority of its analgesic and sedative effect, is known
63 to exhibit certain degree of delay between its concentration-time profile in the blood and
64 that observed in the central nervous system (CNS) [14]. Under such circumstances,
65 assessment of in vivo CNS availability may be of interest, as it is more likely to be
66 directly correlated to the pharmacodynamic effects as compared to blood availability.
67 Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) is one of the biological matrices that can be sampled to
68 provide an overall index of drug access to the CNS after systemic administration of a
69 compound, thus being considered as a surrogate measure for drug concentrations at
70 the target site within the brain [15–17]. Indeed, CSF penetration studies, often in
71 combination with cerebral microdialysis techniques measuring drug concentration in the
72 brain interstitial fluid (ISF), are usually performed in preclinical species to investigate
73 CNS drug distribution, as it is often a good reflection of the situation in humans.[17,18]
74 Consequently, the development of a suitable, selective and sensitive analytical method
75 capable of measuring FEN in both biological fluids is essential for the development of
76 an experimental investigation where CSF and plasma samples are analyzed. Methods
77 of high sensitivity and selectivity are especially required in the case of FEN, since due to
78 its higher potency in comparison with morphine [19–21], effective doses are much lower
79 and, therefore, diminished concentrations (<10 ng/mL) are expected in biological fluids.
80 In addition, the use of high sample volumes is impracticable for PK/PD studies in the

81 newborn, where several samples must be obtained periodically. Consequently, sensitive
82 methods requiring low sample volumes must be used.

83 Some studies for the analysis of FEN in biological samples [22–24], using immunoassay
84 methods have been reported, reaching in the best case a limit of detection of 0.0048
85 ng/mL [25] using 50 μ L of plasma sample. However, these methods are prone to suffer
86 from cross-interference of similar molecules such as structurally related compounds or
87 metabolites[26]. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) methods for the
88 analysis of FEN in plasma [27–29] have also been reported, obtaining values of lowest
89 limit of quantitation (LLOQ) ranging from 0.05 ng/mL up to 4 ng/mL when using a
90 minimum of 500 μ L of plasma. High performance liquid chromatography methods
91 coupled to ultraviolet detection (HPLC-UV) found in literature [30,31] show the same
92 problem, using 1mL of plasma to reach an LLOQ of 0.2ng/mL, in the best case. The
93 only method using a suitable volume of plasma (100 μ L) [32] is not sensitive enough for
94 this PK/PD analysis (LLOQ equal to 3 ng/mL).

95 Several high performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS)
96 methods are available for the determination of FEN and its derivatives in plasma.
97 Methods reported by Koch et al. [33] and Huynh et al. [34] reached LLOQ values as low
98 as 0.02 ng/mL and 0.025 ng/mL, respectively; however, in order to reach those levels
99 1mL of plasma sample and a liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) procedure was required.
100 Lower sample volumes were used by Chang et al. [35] and Hisada et al. [36], using an
101 LLE procedure and a simple protein precipitation method respectively.

102 Studies using HPLC for the quantification of FEN in CSF or brain perfusate samples are
103 scarce [37,38], and to the best of our knowledge, HPLC-MS/MS has not been yet
104 applied to the analysis of FEN in CSF samples from the newborn. The knowledge of
105 drug concentrations in this biological matrix and their relationship to plasma or urine
106 levels would add relevant information towards the establishment of PK/PD correlation
107 for FEN.

108 The aim of this work was to develop an HPLC-MS/MS method with electrospray
109 ionization (ESI) in positive mode that would allow rapid, sensitive and reproducible
110 quantification of fentanyl in plasma and CSF, requiring small sample volume and quick
111 sample processing, for its subsequent application on a PK/PD study of FEN in newborn
112 pigs as an animal model of human neonates.

113 **Material and methods**

114 **Instrumentation**

115 Chromatographic separation was carried out on an Alliance HPLC 2695 separation
116 module (Waters, Milford, MA, USA). A Luna C18 (150 x 2 mm id, 3 μ m)
117 chromatographic column (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) was used as stationary
118 phase. Mass spectrometric analysis was performed using a tandem mass spectrometer
119 Quattro micro (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) equipped with an electrospray ionization
120 source operating in positive mode. Data acquisition was performed using MassLynx 4.0
121 software (Waters, Milford, MA, USA). Sample centrifugation was performed using an
122 Eppendorf 5424 centrifuge (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany).

123 **Reagents and solutions**

124 FEN and $^{13}\text{C}_6\text{FEN}$, used as internal standard, were purchased from Alsachim (Illkirch
125 Graffenstaden, France). HPLC quality formic acid and ammonium formate, from Sigma
126 Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA), were used in the preparation of buffer solutions. LC-MS
127 grade acetonitrile (VWR, Radnor, PA, USA) was used as organic modifier. Purified
128 water from a Milli-Q Element A10 System (Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA) was used in the
129 preparation of buffer and reagent solutions.

130 Drug-free pig plasma samples were purchased from Seralab (West Sussex, United
131 Kingdom) and collected in polypropylene tubes to be frozen at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Due to the lack of
132 drug-free pig CSF samples, artificial CSF was prepared as an aqueous solution of NaCl
133 (147mmol/L), KCl (2.7mmol/L), CaCl_2 (1.2mmol/L) and MgCl_2 (0.85mM).

134 **Preparation of standard solutions and Quality Control (QC) Samples**

135 FEN and $^{13}\text{C}_6\text{FEN}$ were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide to give 1 mg/mL primary stock
136 solutions. A 1000 fold dilution of FEN primary stock solution was made in water to
137 produce a working solution of $1\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$. Aliquots of this working solution were added to
138 drug-free plasma and artificial CSF to obtain Quality Control samples (QCs) at three
139 concentration levels: Low, Mid and High QCs; being the Low QC three times the
140 concentration at the LLOQ, the Mid QC the geometrical mean of the calibration range
141 points, and the High QC the 85% of the upper limit of quantitation (ULOQ). Calibration
142 standards at seven levels ranging from 0.2 to 15 ng/mL for plasma and from 0.25 to 5
143 ng/mL for CSF were prepared also by dilution of working solution with drug-free plasma
144 or CSF. A dilution of the internal standard solution with acetonitrile was made to give a

145 15 ng/mL solution. Primary stock solutions were stored at -20 °C and working solutions
146 were stored at 4 °C until analysis. Calibration standards and QCs were freshly prepared
147 immediately prior to analysis.

148 **Experimental study design**

149 The analytical method developed was used for the quantification of FEN in pig plasma
150 and CSF samples obtained in a prospective study that aimed to investigate the drug
151 PK/PD behaviour when intravenously (i.v.) administered alone (in monotherapy) to
152 mechanically ventilated newborn piglets (2–4 days, 1.7 ± 0.2 kg, $n = 6$) of each gender.
153 The experimental protocol, which is explained in detail somewhere else [39], met
154 European and Spanish regulations for protection of experimental animals (86/609/EEC
155 and RD 1201/2005) and was approved by the Ethical Committee for Animal Welfare of
156 the Cruces University Hospital.

157 FEN dosage regimen (5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bolus immediately followed by a 90 minute infusion of 3
158 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{h}$) was estimated for an adequate degree of sedation, as measured by amplitude-
159 integrated electroencephalography (aEEG), based on the results of a pilot study
160 previously performed in two additional animals (data not shown).

161 Blood samples ($n = 13-15$ per animal) for the quantification of FEN were withdrawn at
162 baseline, immediately after bolus administration, at $t = 1, 10, 30, 90, 95, 120, 150$ and
163 180 minutes after the start of the infusion and then every 30 minutes until experiment
164 was stopped, which occurred at initial signs of awakening shown by each animal (i.e., t
165 = 225-300 minutes). As restricted by the low volume of CSF in the study population as
166 well as by the short evaluation period (maximum of 5 hours), the extraction of a single

167 CSF sample in each animal was considered acceptable from an ethical perspective.
168 CSF sample was drawn either at t = 10, 90 or 150 minutes (2 animals per time point), in
169 order to allow comparison with the simultaneously extracted blood sample.

170 **Sample collection**

171 Samples were collected by the Research Unit for Experimental Neonatal Respiratory
172 Physiology at Cruces University Hospital (Barakaldo, Biscay, Basque Country).

173 Whole arterial blood samples were collected in EDTA tubes, and kept on ice until their
174 immediate centrifugation at 3000 rpm at 4 °C in order to get the plasma. The
175 supernatant was transferred to cryovials and stored at -80 °C until analysed. CSF
176 samples were collected by lumbar puncture and stored in cryovials at -80 °C.

177 **Sample preparation**

178 Frozen samples from the studied subjects were thawed until reaching room
179 temperature. A volume of 150 µL of acetonitrile with a concentration of ¹³C₆FEN of 15
180 ng/mL was added to 100 µL of plasma to promote protein precipitation and was vortex
181 mixed for 5 min. Samples were then centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 5 min. The clean
182 upper layer was transferred to a chromatographic vial to be injected in the HPLC-
183 MS/MS system. CSF samples were injected without any sample preparation except the
184 addition of 5 µL of the ¹³C₆FEN solution in acetonitrile at a concentration of 15 ng/mL to
185 50 µL of sample (final ¹³C₆FEN concentration 1.36 ng/mL). .

186 **Chromatographic and mass spectrometric conditions**

187 Chromatographic separation was achieved using an isocratic method, operating at a
188 flow rate of 0.25 mL/min over a total run time of 3.5 min. The mobile phase was a
189 mixture of acetonitrile and water (40:60 v:v) containing 10 mM of formic acid/ammonium
190 formate buffer, pH 3,5. A sample aliquot of 10 μ L was injected onto the column. The
191 autosampler temperature was set at 10 $^{\circ}$ C and the column was kept at 30 $^{\circ}$ C.

192 Mass spectrometer source temperature was set at 120 $^{\circ}$ C. Nitrogen was used as
193 desolvation gas at a temperature of 300 $^{\circ}$ C and at a flow of 450 L/h. Capillary voltage
194 was set at 0.8 kV. FEN and $^{13}\text{C}_6\text{FEN}$ were detected by multiple reaction monitoring
195 mode (MRM) with a dwell time of 0.20 s. The following transitions were monitored in ESI
196 +: m/z 337.0 \rightarrow 188.0 using a cone voltage (CV) of 35 V and a collision energy (CE) of
197 25 eV for FEN quantification, m/z 337.0 \rightarrow 105.0 using a CV of 25 V and a CE of 45 eV
198 for FEN confirmation and m/z 343.0 \rightarrow 188.0 using a CV of 45 V and a CE of 25 eV for
199 $^{13}\text{C}_6\text{FEN}$.

200 **Validation of HPLC-MS/MS method**

201 The developed method was validated in terms of selectivity, linearity, sensitivity,
202 accuracy, precision, carryover and matrix effect, following the FDA criteria from the
203 Bioanalytical Method Validation Guide [40].

204 The selectivity of the method for plasma was evaluated by comparing the response of
205 six individual drug-free plasma samples against a sample at the lowest limit of
206 quantitation (LLOQ), with reference to potential endogenous and environmental
207 interferences. Due to the absence of blank real samples of CSF, the selectivity of the
208 method in this matrix was evaluated analyzing aliquots of artificial CSF. The signal

209 obtained in the blank matrices must be lower than 20% the response of FEN at the
210 LLOQ and 5% the response of ¹³C₆FEN.

211 Calibration curves—consisting of a blank sample (blank matrix), a zero sample (blank
212 matrix spiked with ¹³C₆FEN), and six non-zero calibration standards—were constructed
213 plotting the corrected peak area of fentanyl (FEN/¹³C₆FEN) against its nominal
214 concentration. The acceptance criterion for the calibration curve was that at least four
215 out of the six non-zero calibration standards had less than 15% deviation from the
216 nominal concentration (20% for LLOQ standard). Sample concentration was calculated
217 by interpolating the resulting corrected area in the regression equation of the calibration
218 curve.

219 Sensitivity was examined by comparing blank samples with the response of calibration
220 standards at the LLOQ, calculated using the Eq 1.

221

$$222 \quad LLOQ = \frac{y_{blank} + 10 \cdot s}{b} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

223 Where y_{blank} is the average signal obtained from six different plasmas or six replicates of
224 artificial CSF, s is its standard deviation and b is the slope of the calibration curve. The
225 analyte response should be at least five times the response obtained from a blank
226 sample.

227 In order to evaluate the intra-day accuracy, five replicate spiked samples were prepared
228 in plasma and CSF at three concentration levels: Low, Mid and High QC; they were
229 analysed in the same day and their concentration value was calculated by interpolating

230 the resulting corrected area in the regression equation of the calibration curve. Accuracy
231 was expressed as relative error (%RE). The acceptance criterion for accuracy was %RE
232 <15%. Inter-day accuracy was determined by calculating the %RE obtained when
233 repeating intra-day accuracy experiments in three different days.

234 Intra and inter-day precision was evaluated as relative standard deviation (%RSD) of
235 five replicates of the Low, Mid and High QCs in three different days, following the same
236 procedure as for accuracy assay. The acceptance criterion for precision was %RSD
237 <15%.

238 Carryover was tested by injection of a blank plasma sample directly after the ULOQ
239 standard injection. The response in the blank sample following the high concentration
240 standard was then compared with the response at the LLOQ, and was considered
241 acceptable if the signal obtained at the FEN and ¹³C₆FEN retention time was under 20%
242 of the signal at the LLOQ and under 5% of the ¹³C₆FEN signal.

243 For the evaluation of matrix effect, five samples of each Low QC, Mid QC and High QC
244 were prepared spiking five different blank plasmas with FEN and ¹³C₆FEN before and
245 after protein precipitation. Normalized matrix factor (NMF) was determined as follows:
246
$$\text{NMF} = (\text{analyte peak area/IS area}) \text{ in matrix} / (\text{analyte peak area/IS area}) \text{ in pure}$$

247 solution. %RSD of the results in different plasma samples was calculated in order to
248 demonstrate the absence of “relative” matrix effect, referring to the variability of matrix
249 effect among different sources of the same matrix. If %RSD was lower than 15%, the
250 method was considered to be free of relative matrix effect.

251 Moreover, matrix effect was also qualitatively studied performing the post-column
252 infusion experiments reported by Bonfiglio et al. [41]. For this purpose, a solution of
253 FEN (10 ng/mL) was infused post-column at a flow rate of 10 μ L/min while the analysis
254 of a blank plasma sample was carried out. The eluent from the column and the flow
255 from the infusion were combined using a zero-dead-volume Tee union and introduced
256 into the source of the mass spectrometer.

257 Results and discussion

258 Chromatographic Behaviour of Fentanyl

259 In the optimum chromatographic conditions the mean retention time of FEN was 2.05
260 min. As expected, the internal standard $^{13}\text{C}_6\text{FEN}$ elutes at the same time as FEN, as
261 can be seen in Figure 1.

262

263 Figure 1. Chromatograms of a blank pig plasma sample, the same sample spiked with 10 ng/mL of
264 $^{13}\text{C}_6\text{FEN}$ and with 0.2 ng/mL of FEN at the LLOQ, and a pig plasma sample from the pharmacokinetic
265 study taken 10 min after the fentanyl bolus dose.

266 Method validation

267 **Selectivity**

268 No interfering peaks were observed at FEN retention time in any of the six individual pig
269 plasma and CSF samples evaluated. For FEN and ¹³C₆FEN the response in blank
270 plasma and CSF samples was lower than 20% and 5%, respectively, of the response at
271 the LLOQ values (0.2 ng/mL for plasma and 0.25 ng/mL for CSF).

272 **Calibration curves and sensitivity**

273 Calibration curves met the criteria established for linearity in the range of 0.2 ng/mL to
274 15 ng/mL for FEN in plasma and 0.25 ng/mL to 5 ng/mL in CSF with values for
275 $R^2 > 0.999$ in all cases. Moreover, the RE value of all the non-zero standards was lower
276 than 15%.

277 **Accuracy and Precision**

278 The results for accuracy and precision are presented in Table 1. Both, in plasma and
279 CSF, the calculated %RE was lower than 15% at the Low, Mid and High QC for both the
280 intra and inter-day assays, evidencing an adequate accuracy along the calibration
281 range. Moreover the %RSD, was smaller than 15% in all QC samples and for both
282 plasma and CSF samples, indicating that the precision of both methods was also
283 suitable.

284

285 Table 1. Intra- and inter-day accuracy and precision in terms of %RE and %RSD, respectively, for plasma
 286 and CSF samples at low, mid and high QC concentration values.

	Plasma				CSF				
	Intra-day		Inter-day		Intra-day		Inter-day		
	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Days 1-3	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Days 1-3	
Low QC (0.5 ng/mL)					Low QC (0.6 ng/mL)				
Mean	0.44	0.54	0.43	0.47	Mean	0.53	0.62	0.62	0.59
%RE	8.17	10.61	2.40	5.67	%RE	12.04	2.58	3.47	2.00
%RSD	9.23	7.45	8.72	12.32	%RSD	14.23	12.69	9.06	8.89
Mid QC (3 ng/mL)					Mid QC (1.2 ng/mL)				
Mean	2.80	2.96	3.33	3.03	Mean	1.12	1.29	1.18	1.20
%RE	6.60	1.25	10.90	0.96	%RE	6.56	7.33	1.86	0.37
%RSD	12.53	3.75	9.48	8.88	%RSD	7.62	9.80	11.66	7.09
High QC (12 ng/mL)					High QC (4.25 ng/mL)				
Mean	12.32	10.73	12.29	11.78	Mean	4.26	4.14	4.41	4.27
%RE	2.67	7.71	13.35	1.85	%RE	0.25	2.53	3.68	3.09
%RSD	12.05	6.55	10.87	7.73	%RSD	4.26	6.43	7.85	0.47

287

288 **Carryover**

289 No quantifiable carryover effect was observed when injecting blank pig plasma or CSF
 290 solution immediately after the ULOQ.

291 **Matrix effect**

292 Postcolumn infusion experiments showed a substantial suppression of the ionization of
 293 FEN due to matrix interferences as it is shown in Figure 2. Notwithstanding, this effect is
 294 compensated by the isotopically labelled internal standard, with the average NMF

295 among the different plasma sources being 93% and presenting a variability, in terms of
296 %RSD, of 9% (n=5).

297 Notably, all parameters (i.e., selectivity, sensitivity, accuracy and precision, carryover
298 and matrix effect) complied with the established acceptance criterion; therefore, the
299 method was successfully validated.

300
301 Figure 2. Injection of 5 blank plasmas with postcolumn infusion of FEN (continuous lines) and injection of
302 a blank plasma spiked with FEN at a concentration of 10 ng/mL (dashed line).

303 **Analysis of samples from PK/PD experimental study**

304 The optimized HPLC-MS/MS method was implemented for the measurement of FEN
305 concentration in pig plasma and CSF samples obtained from a PK/PD experimental
306 study performed in newborn piglets [39].

307 The developed method enabled the quantification of FEN concentrations from as low as
308 0.2 ng/mL, thus allowing the characterization of the plasma profiles in piglets (Figure 3).
309 Most plasma concentrations calculated were above the LLOQ, except for the latest

310 sampling points of two of the pigs in the study (no.3 and no.6), when FEN is supposed
311 to have already been eliminated.

312
313 Figure 3. Individual plasma profiles (black dots) and concentration measured in the available single CSF
314 sample (white squares) of FEN in piglets as quantified by the developed HPLC-MS/MS method. FEN
315 level in the CSF sample extracted from pig No. 6 was below the LLOQ and could therefore not be
316 displayed.

317 The plasma concentration time curves obtained in animals revealed multi-exponential
318 disposition kinetics as expected, displaying a rapid initial distribution phase (compatible
319 with high lipophilicity of FEN) followed by a slower decline. Although FEN plasma levels
320 showed quite a large interindividual variability, overall it had virtually been cleared up by

321 the end of the experiments (225-300 min), which is consistent with animals showing
322 initial signs of awakening at this point.

323 Fentanyl is primarily eliminated from the body by hepatic N-dealkylation via CYP3A4 to
324 the inactive metabolite norfentanyl [42–44], which is subsequently excreted in urine
325 accounting for roughly 94% of the dose. The remaining percentage of the dose is
326 excreted unchanged in urine and stool [45,46], so that quantification of the metabolites
327 in study samples was deemed purposeless.

328 FEN was also determined in CSF samples and was detected from all of them, with the
329 exception of the one taken at 150 min from pig no. 6, whose plasma FEN concentration
330 was also below the LLOQ by that time. In the remaining CSF samples FEN was
331 detected even at the first time point (10 minutes post-dose) (Figure 4), thus confirming
332 the rapid access of the compound to the CNS, in line with its high lipophilicity.

333 The CSF/plasma ratio provides insight into the CNS drug exposure or availability of
334 centrally active compounds, thus serving as a reference for assessing the extent of
335 delivery to the pharmacological targets within the CNS (biophase or effect site). This is
336 especially true for those drugs crossing the blood brain barrier (BBB) mainly by diffusion
337 via the transcellular route after systemic administration [12,14], which seems to be the
338 case for FEN in line with its high lipophilicity and the apparent lack of active transport at
339 the level of BBB. Indeed, FEN has proved not to behave as a substrate of main
340 transporters including efflux P-glycoprotein or influx organic anion-transporting
341 polypeptide (OATP) [47,48].

342 The comparison of CSF and plasma concentrations is particularly applicable in
343 elucidating the lag in the time course of a central pharmacologic effect relative to that of
344 drug concentration in circulation, under the assumption that CSF is in equilibrium with
345 the biophase [14]. Even if care should be taken when interpreting data with only a single
346 time point CSF and plasma concentration available, this is, to the best of our
347 knowledge, one of the first reports on the temporal inter-relationship of FEN plasma and
348 CSF kinetics after i.v. administration of such low doses in preclinical species. Up to
349 date, two single reports have been found in scientific literature describing this
350 relationship in experimental animal models, but they refer to the administration of doses
351 far higher than the ones concerned herein. The first one was performed in dogs injected
352 tritium-labeled ³H-FEN (10 or 100 µg/kg) [49], and the second one applied HPLC-UV to
353 the quantification of FEN only at steady state conditions in piglets administered 30 µg/kg
354 bolus followed by infusion at 10 µg/kg/h [38].

355 In this sense, there also seems to be a paucity of published data on methods of analysis
356 using HPLC-MS/MS for the quantification of FEN in CSF or cerebral microdialysis
357 samples, despite the importance of determining the drug levels in the CNS with a
358 sufficient degree of sensitivity. Even though in the present study only one CSF sample
359 was obtained from each subject, the low volume of CSF needed (50 µL) allows the
360 applicability of the method in future and more specific pharmacokinetic studies aimed to
361 further evaluate the CSF distribution of FEN in larger preclinical populations and/or
362 under different dosing protocols. The low volume of CSF needed (50 µL) eases the
363 application of this method to the analysis of samples of the newborn. For instance, the
364 performance of frequent serial CSF sampling over time would allow the calculation of

365 the relative CSF exposure as compared to plasma, which is given by the ratio between
366 the corresponding areas under the curve (AUC_{CSF}/AUC_{plasma} ratio). Moreover, this
367 HPLC-MS/MS method could also be applied to the quantification of FEN levels in ISF
368 samples obtained via microdialysis techniques, thus providing the tool for the joint
369 assessment of PK disposition in both matrixes. This could help elucidating the existing
370 PK inter-relationship of FEN concentrations in plasma, CSF and brain ISF, against the
371 observed pharmacodynamic effects in suitable animal models [17,18,50]. This PK/PD
372 correlation may then be extrapolated to humans based on the well-described predictive
373 capacity of some preclinical species [14,15], which is of great value in view of the
374 extremely restricted access to sampling of these biophase surrogate markers (i.e., CSF
375 and brain ISF as indicative of drug levels at the effect site) in humans.

376 **Conclusion**

377 A simple, selective and sensitive HPLC-MS/MS method was developed and validated
378 for the quantitative determination of FEN in pig plasma and CSF samples, which could
379 be applied in future pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic assays.

380 This assay requires only a small volume of plasma (100 μ L) and CSF (50 μ L), which is
381 of particular advantage in cases where sample volumes are limited (e.g., paediatric
382 preclinical studies). The suitability of the method was assessed by its successful
383 application to samples of both types of biological fluid from a pharmacokinetic study
384 performed in newborn piglets.

385 **Acknowledgements**

386 Authors thank the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (Project CTQ2009-11690
387 and INNPACTO Project, ITP-09000-2010-002, which is financed by the FEDER Fund),
388 University of the Basque Country (UFI 11/23 and Project PPM12/06) and Basque
389 Country Government (Project IT789/13) for financial support and the SGIker technical
390 support (UPV/ EHU, MICINN, GV/EJ, ERDF and ESF). E. Encinas, E. Rico, M.E.
391 Blanco and O. Gonzalez also thank Basque Country Government and UPV/EHU for
392 their predoctoral and postdoctoral grants. We also want to thank the staff of the
393 Research Unit for Experimental Neonatal Respiratory Physiology at Cruces University
394 Hospital (Barakaldo, Biscay, Basque Country) for executing the experimental phase in
395 piglets.

396 **References**

- 397 [1] J.H. Kim, S.Y. Jang, M.J. Kim, S.Y. Lee, J.S. Yoon. Comparison of Pain-relieving
398 Effects of Fentanyl versus Ketorolac after Eye Amputation Surgery. Korean J
399 Ophthalmol. 2013,27,229.
- 400 [2] J.V. Aranda, W. Carlo, P. Hummel, R. Thomas, V.T. Lehr, K.J. Anard. Analgesia and
401 sedation during mechanical ventilation in neonates. Clin Ther. 2005,27,877.
- 402 [3] M.D. Twite, A. Rashid, J. Zuk, R.H. Friesen. Sedation, analgesia, and neuromuscular
403 blockade in the pediatric intensive care unit: survey of fellowship training programs.
404 Pediatr Crit Care Med. 2004,5,521.
- 405 [4] E. Encinas, R. Calvo, J.C. Lukas, V. Vozmediano, M. Rodriguez, E. Suarez. A
406 predictive pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic model of fentanyl for analgesia/sedation
407 in neonates based on a semi-physiologic approach. Paediatr. Drugs. 2013, 15, 247.
- 408 [5] P. Anzenbacher, P. Soucek, E. Anzenbacherova, I. Gut, K. Hruby, Z. Svoboda, J.
409 Kvetina. Presence and activity of cytochrome P450 isoforms in minipig liver
410 microsomes. Comparison with human liver samples. Drug Metab. Dispos. 1998, 26, 56.
- 411 [6] M.M. Swindle, A. Makin, A.J. Herron, F.J. Clubb Jr., K.S. Frazier. Swine as models in
412 biomedical research and toxicology testing. Vet. Pathol. 2012, 49, 344.

- 413 [7] F. Caminita, M. van der Merwe, B. Hance, R. Krishnan, S. Miller, K.K. Buddington,
414 R.K. Buddington. A preterm pig model of lung immaturity and spontaneous infant
415 respiratory distress syndrome. *Am. J. Physiol. Lung Cell. Mol. Physiol.* 2015, 308, 118.
- 416 [8] R.K. Buddington, P.T. Sangild, B. Hance, E.Y. Huang, D.D. Black. Prenatal
417 gastrointestinal development in the pig and responses after preterm birth. *J. Anim. Sci.*
418 2012, 90, 290.
- 419 [9] Y.A. Eiby, L.L. Wright, V.P. Kalanjati, S.M. Miller, S.T. Bjorkman, H.L. Keates, E.R.
420 Lumbers, P.B. Colditz, B.E. Lingwood. A pig model of the preterm neonate:
421 Anthropometric and physiological characteristics. *PLoS One.* 2013, 8, e68763.
- 422 [10] H.G. Fritz, M. Holzmayr, B. Walter, K.U. Moeritz, A. Lupp, R. Bauer. The effect of
423 mild hypothermia on plasma fentanyl concentration and biotransformation in juvenile
424 pigs. *Anesth. Analg.* 2005, 100, 996.
- 425 [11] M.T. Skaanild. Porcine cytochrome P450 and metabolism. *Curr. Pharm. Des.* 2006,
426 12, 1421.
- 427 [12] W.J. Roth, C.B. Kissinger, R.R. McCain, B.R. Cooper, J.N. Marchant-Forde, R.C.
428 Vreeman, S. Hannou, G.T. Knipp. Assessment of juvenile pigs to serve as human
429 pediatric surrogates for preclinical formulation pharmacokinetic testing. *AAPS J.* 2013,
430 15, 763.
- 431 [13] R.A. Schieber, R.L. Stiller, D.R. Cook. Cardiovascular and pharmacodynamic
432 effects of high-dose fentanyl in newborn piglets. *Anesthesiology.* 1985, 63, 166.
- 433 [14] J. Lotsch, C. Walter, M.J. Parnham, B.G. Oertel, G. Geisslinger. Pharmacokinetics
434 of non-intravenous formulations of fentanyl. *Clin. Pharmacokinet.* 2013, 52, 23.
- 435 [15] E.C. de Lange, M. Danhof. Considerations in the use of cerebrospinal fluid
436 pharmacokinetics to predict brain target concentrations in the clinical setting:
437 Implications of the barriers between blood and brain. *Clin. Pharmacokinet.* 2002, 41,
438 691.
- 439 [16] A. Gottas, E.L. Oiestad, F. Boix, A. Ripel, C.H. Thaulow, B.S. Pettersen, V.
440 Vindenes, J. Morland. Simultaneous measurement of heroin and its metabolites in brain
441 extracellular fluid by microdialysis and ultra performance liquid chromatography tandem
442 mass spectrometry. *J. Pharmacol. Toxicol. Methods.* 2012, 66, 14.
- 443 [17] D.D. Shen, A.A. Artru, K.K. Adkison. Principles and applicability of CSF sampling for
444 the assessment of CNS drug delivery and pharmacodynamics. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.*
445 2004, 56, 1825.[18] J.H. Lin. CSF as a surrogate for assessing CNS exposure: An
446 industrial perspective. *Curr. Drug Metab.* 2008, 9, 46.
- 447 [19] J.L. Lichtor, F.B. Sevarino, G.P. Joshi, M.A. Busch, E. Nordbrock, B. Ginsberg. The
448 relative potency of oral transmucosal fentanyl citrate compared with intravenous

- 449 morphine in the treatment of moderate to severe postoperative pain. *Anesth. Analg.*
450 1999, 89, 732.
- 451 [20] G.W. Hanks, F. Conno, N. Cherny, M. Hanna, E. Kalso, H.J. McQuay, S.
452 Mercadante, J. Meynadier, P. Poulain, C. Ripamonti, L. Radbruch, J.R. Casas, J. Sawe,
453 R.G. Twycross, V. Ventafridda. Expert working group of the research network of the
454 European Association for Palliative. Morphine and alternative opioids in cancer pain:
455 The EAPC recommendations. *Brit. J. Cancer.* 2001, 84, 587.
- 456 [21] A. Paix, A. Coleman, J. Lees, J. Grigson, M. Brooksbank, D. Thorne, M. Ashby.
457 Subcutaneous fentanyl and sufentanil infusion substitution for morphine intolerance in
458 cancer pain management. *Pain.* 1995, 63, 263.
- 459 [22] M.L. Snyder, P. Jarolim, S.E. Melanson. A new automated urine fentanyl
460 immunoassay: Technical performance and clinical utility for monitoring fentanyl
461 compliance. *Clin. Chim. Acta.* 2011, 412, 946.
- 462 [23] G. Wang, K. Huynh, R. Barhate, W. Rodrigues, C. Moore, C. Coulter, M. Vincent, J.
463 Soares. Development of a homogeneous immunoassay for the detection of fentanyl in
464 urine. *Forensic Sci. Int.* 2011, 206, 127.
- 465 [24] W.L. Wang, E.J. Cone, J. Zacny. Immunoassay evidence for fentanyl in hair of
466 surgery patients. *Forensic Sci. Int.* 1993, 61, 65.
- 467 [25] Y. Dotsikas, Y.L. Loukas, I. Siafaka. Determination of umbilical cord and maternal
468 plasma concentrations of fentanyl by using novel spectrophotometric and
469 chemiluminescence enzyme immunoassays. *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 2002, 459, 177.
- 470 [26] M.H. Kroll, R.J. Elin. Interference with clinical laboratory analyses. *Clin. Chem.*
471 1994, 40, 1996.
- 472 [27] H. Bagheri, A. Es-haghi, F. Khalilian, M.R. Rouini. Determination of fentanyl in
473 human plasma by head-space solid-phase microextraction and gas chromatography-
474 mass spectrometry. *J. Pharmaceut. Biomed.* 2007, 43, 1763.
- 475 [28] A.H. Malkawi, A.M. Al-Ghananeem, P.A. Crooks. Development of a GCMS assay for
476 the determination of fentanyl pharmacokinetics in rabbit plasma after sublingual spray
477 delivery. *AAPS J.* 2008, 10, 261.
- 478 [29] A. Szeitz, K.W. Riggs, C. Harvey-Clark. Sensitive and selective assay for fentanyl
479 using gas chromatography with mass selective detection. *J. Chromatogr. B Biomed.*
480 *Appl.* 1996, 675, 33.
- 481 [30] E.J. Portier, K. de Blok, J.J. Butter, C.J. van Boxtel. Simultaneous determination of
482 fentanyl and midazolam using high-performance liquid chromatography with ultraviolet
483 detection. *J. Chromatogr. B Biomed. Sci. Appl.* 1999, 723, 313.

- 484 [31] K. Kumar, J.A. Ballantyne, A.B. Baker. A sensitive assay for the simultaneous
485 measurement of alfentanil and fentanyl in plasma. *J. Pharmaceut. Biomed.* 1996, 14,
486 667.
- 487 [32] A.A. Almousa, R. Ikeda, M. Wada, N. Kuroda, R.K. Hanajiri, K. Nakashima. HPLC-
488 UV method development for fentanyl determination in rat plasma and its application to
489 elucidate pharmacokinetic behavior after i.p. administration to rats. *J. Chromatogr. B*
490 *Analyt. Technol. Biomed. Life Sci.* 2011, 879, 2941.
- 491 [33] D.E. Koch, R. Isaza, J.W. Carpenter, R.P. Hunter. Simultaneous extraction and
492 quantitation of fentanyl and norfentanyl from primate plasma with LC/MS detection. *J.*
493 *Pharmaceut. Biomed.* 2004, 34, 577.
- 494 [34] N.H. Huynh, N. Tyrefors, L. Ekman, M. Johansson. Determination of fentanyl in
495 human plasma and fentanyl and norfentanyl in human urine using LC-MS/MS. *J.*
496 *Pharmaceut. Biomed.* 2005, 37, 1095.
- 497 [35] Y.W. Chang, H.T. Yao, Y.S. Chao, T.K. Yeh. Rapid and sensitive determination of
498 fentanyl in dog plasma by on-line solid-phase extraction integrated with a hydrophilic
499 column coupled to tandem mass spectrometry. *J. Chromatogr. B Analyt. Technol.*
500 *Biomed. Life Sci.* 2007, 857, 195.
- 501 [36] T. Hisada, M. Katoh, K. Hitoshi, Y. Kondo, M. Fujioka, Y. Toyama, H. Ieda, S.
502 Gocho, M. Nadai. A simple liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry method
503 for determination of plasma fentanyl concentration in rats and patients with cancer pain.
504 *Biol. Pharm. Bull.* 2013, 36, 412.
- 505 [37] C. Dagenais, C.L. Graff, G.M. Pollack. Variable modulation of opioid brain uptake
506 by P-glycoprotein in mice. *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 2004, 67, 269.
- 507 [38] H.D. Modanlou, T. Pan, H. Riaz, T. Samson, R. Sheikh, K. Beharry. Effects of
508 continuous infusion fentanyl citrate on cerebrovascular and systemic prostanooids in
509 postsurgical newborn piglets. *J. Investig. Med.* 1996, 44, 362.
- 510 [39] C. Rey-Santano, V. Mielgo, I.S.A. Valls, E. Encinas, J.C. Lukas, V. Vozmediano, E.
511 Suarez. Evaluation of fentanyl disposition and effects in newborn piglets as an
512 experimental model for human neonates. *PLoS One.* 2014, 9, e90728.
- 513 [40] Guidance for Industry: Bioanalytical Method Validation. U.S. Department of Health
514 and Human Services, Food and Drug Administration, Center for Drug Evaluation and
515 Research (CDER), Center for Veterinary Medicine (CVM), Rockville, MD, May, 2001.
- 516 [41] R. Bonfiglio, R.C. King, T.V. Olah, K. Merkle. The effects of sample preparation
517 methods on the variability of the electrospray ionization response for model drug
518 compounds. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 1999, 13, 1175.
- 519 [42] E. Schneider, K. Brune. Opioid activity and distribution of fentanyl metabolites.
520 *Naunyn Schmiedebergs Arch. Pharmacol.* 1986, 334, 267.

- 521 [43] S. Grape, S.A. Schug, S. Lauer, B.S. Schug. Formulations of fentanyl for the
522 management of pain. *Drugs*. 2010, 70, 57.
- 523 [44] H. Shankaran, F. Adeshina, J.G. Teeguarden. Physiologically-based
524 pharmacokinetic model for Fentanyl in support of the development of provisional
525 advisory levels. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 2013, 273, 464.
- 526 [45] D.E. Feierman, J.M. Lasker. Metabolism of fentanyl, a synthetic opioid analgesic,
527 by human liver microsomes. Role of CYP3A4. *Drug Metab. Dispos.* 1996, 24, 932.
- 528 [46] R.B. Labroo, M.F. Paine, K.E. Thummel, E.D. Kharasch. Fentanyl metabolism by
529 human hepatic and intestinal cytochrome P450 3A4: Implications for interindividual
530 variability in disposition, efficacy, and drug interactions. *Drug Metab. Dispos.* 1997, 25,
531 1072.
- 532 [47] C.Wandel, R. Kim, M.Wood, A.Wood. Interaction of morphine, fentanyl, sufentanil,
533 alfentanil, and loperamide with the efflux drug transporter P-glycoprotein.
534 *Anesthesiology*. 2002, 96, 913.
- 535 [48] V. C. Ziesenitz, S.K. Konig, N. Mahlke, R. Jantos, G. Skopp, J. Weiss, W.E. Haefeli,
536 G.Mikus. Fentanyl pharmacokinetics is not dependent on hepatic uptake by organic
537 anion-transporting polypeptide 1B1 in human beings. *Basic Clin. Pharmacol. Toxicol.*
538 2013, 113, 43.
- 539 [49] C.C. Hug Jr., M.R. Murphy. Fentanyl disposition in cerebrospinal fluid and plasma
540 and its relationship to ventilatory depression in the dog. *Anesthesiology*. 1979, 50, 342.
- 541 [50] Y. Nagaya, Y. Nozaki, K. Kobayashi, O. Takenaka, Y. Nakatani, K. Kusano, T.
542 Yoshimura, H. Kusuhara. Utility of cerebrospinal fluid drug concentration as a surrogate
543 for unbound brain concentration in nonhuman primates. *Drug Metab. Pharmacokinet.*
544 2014, 29, 419.